

Impact of the Dynamic Application Artisans India in the Global E-Commerce Industry for users and Artisans alike an Application Connecting Consumers with Artisans Making Handmade Artifacts Representing the Face of Indian Culture

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Abstract:- The purpose of the current study was to analyse the impacts of the application called “ArtisansIndia” in the E-Commerce Industry. ArtisansIndia is a proposed platform that allows Artisans to promote their businesses for free to attract global customers and facilitate legitimate trade. It is currently in development that will help Artisans from India to connect with global consumers to provide essential business to craftsmen. This will eventually be helpful in promoting the economy of the cottage industries. During the development of this application, several factors were considered such as the deployment of product in specific regions, customs regulations of other countries and language inclusion. The main focus of the application is to prevent barriers, to facilitate easier transactions, communications and well-catered payment gateway methods with subscription services to enrich a customer’s experience.

Keywords:- E-Commerce Industry, Artisans, Deployment, Transactions and Subscription Services.

I. INTRODUCTION

As the world braced the wrath of the COVID 19 pandemic, professionals were made redundant. Some industries became virtually non-existent because borders were closed. Panic set on and spread like wildfire. Front line workers risked their lives to save others and businesses took unspeakable hits and losses repeatedly for a solid time of two years. Industries on the penurious side of the economic spectrum and ones who relied heavily on the tourism/travel industry and the cash movement sector in regards with the stock market got effected badly. Moreover, the farmers were a big portion of the affected individuals. As an effect of the pandemic, USD 2.96 Trillion (\$2,960,000,000,000) was virtually wiped from the Global GDP as the forecasted loss stood at 3.4% (Szmigiera, 2021). About half the adults who were made redundant due to the epidemic are still unemployed and are not able to locate new job opportunities due to the travel restrictions imposed (Parker et al. 2020). Artisans and Craftsmen were affected in India as the industry suffered major losses as travel restrictions were posted and

less tourists visited the country. Many artisans had to give up their jobs of making generation old handicrafts and move to urban areas to find jobs. This displaced families, caused problems in the distribution of materials, and give rise to losses for shipping companies and the producers of raw materials. Due to mass displacement and sudden changes in the Artisan chain of supply, the dominoes began to fall and one problem caused the rise of another. Many artisans moving to urban areas to locate jobs caused severe food shortages, housing and sanitary issues. Such a drastic change placed a lot of pressure on the government and the municipalities of the regions.

To help artisans get back to their roots of the creation of truly fine handicrafts, team of authors named Dominating Entrepreneurs has decided to create Artisans India, a platform which allows Artisans to promote their businesses for free to attract global customers and facilitate legitimate trade. The aim of the studies is to analyze the impact of an application called Artisans India in the Global E-commerce industry for Users and Artisans.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The design of the application is based on an outline of backstage actions that includes the agreement with artisans, verifying artisans, providing a stable and secured platform and enriching customers’ experiences by making the application convenient and user friendly. The visual design was created using Adobe XD to give the users a perspective for the front-end design whereas the functionality of the backend is still in development. The contact of Artisans in India will be done through mutual and indirect ways with the assistance of specific people who are able to communicate and contact the Artisan. Since the application relies on customer necessities and wants so feedback is generated through poles and feedback requests to increase customer satisfaction.

To generate sufficient revenue, the partnerships will be created. The generated investments will help flourish the growth of industry at an exponential rate. The partnerships will be in the form of specific deals with shipping organizations and software services to bear the cost of

logistics. The average price of a handicraft is calculated by researching, visiting different real life places like global village in Dubai and communicating with real life artisans in India. The mean of the mean of the artifacts is calculated and discounted by 15-20% to remove if there are any gross profit to ensure that the price would be coming from the artisans themselves. Hence, mean price decided for handicraft is 50USD as a mean price.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research shows an estimated growth of 5% in product sales, in the Artisan industry in India (Milne, and Clark et al. 2021). Due to the increase in demand for online shopping, this product impacts the artisan industry in a very positive way. Considering the incrementing interest towards online shopping/purchasing, this application will be impacting the artisans industry by utilizing a positive approach. Sale to download ratio stands at 45:1000 i.e. for every 1000 client downloads, 45 clients are engaging in businesses (Saleh, 2020). In the wake of research, it has been found that high demand and a low number of business platforms in the Artisans Industry would be success factor in helpful to launch and expand such application. By calculating the previous data from research and by prosperous marketing strategies it has been estimated an approximate value of 300 downloads in the launch year and an exponential increase by about 45% for the second year, and about 55% for every year following the second year. Hence, based on survey, it is estimated that 600-700 downloads would be made, with around 30-40 clients being regular customers to the Artisan Industry of India by the end of 2024. All of the numerical effects have been stated and reviewed such as the revenue generated referring to the amount of money transacted through ArtisansIndia as well the number of downloads showcasing the number of customers the Artisans will cater to. The results are shown in Figure 1 and 2. Finally, it is estimated that approximately \$2,000 in revenue contributing to being a profitable business in the Artisan Industry of India by the end of 2024. It is calculated through estimated formulas such as sale to download ratio multiplied by the number of downloads to get the number of estimated customers and revenue alike

Fig.1: Estimated downloads worldwide showing exponential increase in customers

Fig. 2: Estimated Sales worldwide showing exponential increase in revenue generated

IV. EFFECT OF ARTISANS INDIA

- *For Consumers:* Consumers all around the world are predicted to be able to connect and contact Artisans from all parts of India regarding their products, materials and other specifics. Consumers will also be able to buy individual handcrafted and handmade products or have (an) item(s) tailored to their likings and specifications. They will be able to experience the true culture and tradition of the vastly diverse country of India, featuring the influence of many regions, religions, cultures and materials.
- *For Artisans:* Artisans will be able to return to fulfil important jobs in our society, to preserve our cultures and roots a well as helping promote our cultures. It has been concluded that through ArtisansIndia, many craftsmen and Artisans will be able to post pictures and details of their products for sale as well as connecting with customers to provide the best quality and the perfect tailor-made products. This will allow Artisans to share their works and arts with the rest of the world, and thus inviting more customers which will be beneficial to the growth of the application and the industry, and more importantly, help the Artisans have an adequate source of income.

The first beta version of the user interface has been tested with around 15-20 people with positive comments and valuable feedback. The estimated growth was based upon the data of previous endeavors, feedback and comments of consumers as well as mathematical estimations. The application is due to be available on the App Store and the Play Store for download as well as on the internet on a web version. The proposed application page is shown in Figures 3 to 7.

Fig. 3: Dashboard of the application, ArtisansIndia

Fig. 4: & Fig. 5: Showcasing the language and currency choices being implemented to allow for a wider array of customers

Fig. 6: Example of an Artisan’s Page

Fig. 7: Search Bar helping customers navigate

V. CONCLUSION

“ArtisansIndia” application is proposed with a goal of preventing exploitation and promoting decent hard work in E-Commerce Industry. From the analytics and data, it is concluded that there is a positive impact of “ArtisansIndia” in the Indian Artisan Industry. Research shows a prosperous economic development in the industry, satisfying demands and meeting expectations of a wide array of customers. Many downloads coupled with attractive and legitimate marketing strategies are a core of a successful application with respect to the E-Commerce Industry and the Artisan business.

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